

Table 1. Maintainers and restorers* for V20 A at RRS, Mandya, Karnataka, India, 1992.

Male parent	Maintainer or restorer	Male parent	Maintainer or restorer
ES18	M	IRBPHN 89	R
Pragathi	M	Doddbya	PR
Mutshell	M	CR 213-1002	R
Kembasadi	M	BRB11-461	PR
Karolina	R	T2934	PR
Kumbara	R	BPT 4339	PR
Kempavadi	R	BR51-91-7	PR
Bhavani	R	BR51-46-5	PR
Salumpikit	R	IET11668	M
Vani	R	IET9801	M
China 6	R	IET11683	M
Hurigidda	PR	IET10897	M
Mahaveera	PR	IET10857	M
Akashi	PR	IET10408	M
Vikram	PR	IET7511	M
Mangala	PR	IET11689	M
Kirwana	PR	IET11691	R
Shakti	PR	IET10410	R
Maratibatha	PR	IET10892	R
Mahsuri	PR	IET10891	R
Bilikagga	PR	IET2934	R
BKB	PR	IET10890	R
PSP5-2-2	PR	IET5656	R
Pushpa	PR	IET7191	R
Tellahamsa	PR	IET8116	R
IET10882	PR	IR51315-4-5	R
IET10409	PR	IR9876-211-26	R
IET9831	PR	IR9852-18-1	R
IET10884	PR	IR9511-122-3	R
IR28237-31-3-2-1	M	IR31429-18-4	R
IR28178-111-1-2-3	M	IR28210-68-4	PR
IR31916-9-2	R	IR18353-33-1	PR
IR30864	R	IR29692-71-2-2-2	PR
IR22107-41-1-2	R	IR9469-62-4	PR
IR25861-35-3-3	R	IR21916-128-3	PR
IR25167-9-4	R	IR18356-932-4	PR
IR19661-1-3	R	IR22107-14-2-1	PR
IR31358-90-2	R	IR28178-28-6	PR
IR26924-92-1-3	R	IR21819-20	PR
IR26	R	IR20226-24-7	PR
IR13240-32-6	R	IR32420-130-1-3	PR
IR21178-39-4	R	IR5294-67-3-6	PR
IR21573-2-1-22	R	IR2863-39-2-8	PR
IR25683-8-4-6	R	IR27280-39-9	PR
IR13419-113-3	R		

*M = maintainer, R = restorer, PR = partial restorer.

Table 2. Frequency of restorers and maintainers in cultures of Indian and IRRI origin.

Source	Main-tainers (no.)	Restorers (no.)	Partial restorers (no.)	Total (no.)
IRRI	2	21	14	37
India	12	16	24	52

and more than 99% spikelet sterility as maintainers. Restorers were those showing more than 90% pollen and spikelet fertility. The rest were partial restorers.

Among the 89 cultures tested, 14 were maintainers, 37 restorers, and 38 partial restorers (Table 1). The frequency of maintainers was greater in Indian cultures than in IRRI cultures (Table 2). ■

Using androgenesis in indica rice breeding

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The frequency of whole plantlet induction through androgenesis is still very low in indica rice: about 1%, based on anther number. While increasing the frequency to 1.7%, we studied the application of androgenesis to breeding.

After surface sterilization, anthers of indica rice hybrids were cultured on N6 medium to which 2 mg 2,4-D/liter was added to induce calli, and then on N6 + Kin 2 + NAA 0.5 + IAA 0.5 mg/liter to regenerate plantlets. Progenies of the doubled haploid plants (H2) were assessed for yield potential, resistance to pests, and grain quality, and then testcrossed with male sterile lines to screen for restorers.

We examined 654 pollen lines (H2) derived from hybrid rice and found that the frequency of homozygous diploids was 88.6%. Statistical analysis revealed that the characters within one line are relatively uniform and stably heritable. Among different lines, broad genetic recombinations occur. We conclude that using androgenesis in indica rice breeding is feasible.

Gan Zhao Xian No. 11, an early-maturing indica that was registered in 1990, is an example of a variety that was successfully bred through anther culture of hybrid rice Shan You No. 2. Duration is only about 105 d and yield about 5.6-6 t/ha. It has high cold tolerance at the seedling stage and uniform heading and ripening.

Restorer line 2374, which has good restoring ability and strong combining ability, was bred from progenies of Shan 2 H2 (a pollen line)/Jian 30. This line gives strong heterosis in crosses with Xie Qin Zhao A, Di Gu A, and a photoperiod-sensitive genetic male sterile line. The hybrid rice Xie 2374, which was registered in 1990, has high yield potential, broad adaptability, and broad resistance to diseases and insects.

HR1004 was bred through anther culture of CPSLO 17/Skybonnet (F₁). It has high grain quality, wide compatibility, and CMS restoring ability. Protein content is up to 12.9% and amylose content is 17.4%. Grain is long

and thin (length:width ratio is 3.6), and not chalky. When it was crossed with Xie Qin Zhao A or Chang Fei 22 A, the hybrid showed high quality in grain appearance and edibility.

Using androgenesis of indica rice to

induce pollen plantlets and improve varieties is an effective breeding path. Further studies are needed, however, to improve the frequency of green plantlet induction in indica rice. ■

Identification of cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) sources in rice through reciprocal crosses

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Many rice varieties of different origins were crossed during 1988-90. Some seed parents have shown a dramatic cytoplasmic effect on F₁ fertility when crossed with pollen parents.

We used tester parents PAL, 2159, 029, 02428, Ys 8072, Ys 8804, LH422, and Reed rice (Table 1) to make reciprocal crosses in 1991. Each cross was planted in a single row of 15 plants with 25- × 20-cm spacing in Nanjing (32° N). The F₁ pollen fertility was checked.

We observed significant reciprocal difference in both pollen and spikelet fertility in four of the six reciprocal crosses involving PAL as the seed parent (Table 2). A similar difference existed in two of the three crosses involving Reed rice as maternal parent. The six crosses with either PAL or Reed rice cytoplasm were completely sterile in both pollen fertility and seed setting of bagged panicles. The corresponding crosses with either PAL or Reed rice as pollen parents showed normal fertility.

The natural outcrossing rate varied greatly among crosses showing fertility in F₁. The outcrossing rate of PAL/2159 and Reed rice/2159 was high and significantly higher than that of PAL/029, PAL/02428, PAL/Ys 8072, and Reed rice/Ys 8072 (Table 2). Because 2159 seems to have enhanced outcrossing, 2159 may be used as a maintainer to develop PAL and Reed rice CMS lines.

The remaining three reciprocal crosses of PAL/LH422, PAL/Ys 8804, and Reed

Table 1. Characteristics of parents used in crosses.

Parent	Varietal group ^a	Pedigree or origin	Remarks ^b
2159	I	NJ11/IR29	
PAL	I	Palgarh 31-1-3	
Reed rice	I	Reed-like wild rice(?)/IR24	
029	J	Luai//IR8/Nongkeng 58///IR36///ASD7	WC
02428	J	Jipangdao/Pangxiegu	WC
Ys 8072	J	020/729	WC
Ys 8804	J	Nankeng 35/020	WC
LH422	M	Hunan Hybrid Rice Center, China	WC

^aI = indica, J = japonica, M = intermediate. ^bWC = wide compatibility.

Table 2. Pollen fertility and percent seed setting in reciprocal crosses of rice varieties.

Cross	Pollen ^a	Seed setting (%)	
		Bagged panicles	Natural outcrossing
2159/PAL	F	88.63 ± 7.31	85.29 ± 8.13
PAL/2159	CS	0	65.59 ± 7.88
029/PAL	F	72.46 ± 8.91	78.51 ± 7.10
PAL/029	CS	0	16.78 ± 9.01
02428/PAL	F	75.38 ± 7.21	79.18 ± 6.76
PAL/02428	CS	0	10.33 ± 5.72
Ys 8072/PAL	F	68.78 ± 7.83	79.44 ± 3.83
PAL/Ys 8072	CS	0	32.38 ± 15.44
LH422/PAL	F	75.60 ± 6.82	74.38 ± 0.14
PAL/LH422	F	78.23 ± 4.32	72.29 ± 3.83
Ys 8804/PAL	F	74.21 ± 3.78	77.60 ± 5.39
PAL/Ys 8804	F	64.28 ± 8.11	62.23 ± 11.99
2159/Reed rice	F	78.43 ± 3.78	88.01 ± 4.37
Reed rice/2159	CS	0	57.39 ± 4.75
Ys 8072/Reed rice	F	65.32 ± 4.58	68.88 ± 7.48
Reed rice/Ys 8072	CS	0	28.18 ± 13.07
LH422/Reed rice	F	64.21 ± 4.33	63.41 ± 5.62
Reed rice/LH422	F	73.78 ± 5.31	75.32 ± 4.73

^aF = fertile (>90% fertility), CS = completely sterile (<1% fertility).

rice/LH422 were highly fertile (Table 2). Results suggest that LH422 has Rf gene(s) that can restore fertility for PAL and Reed rice sterile cytoplasm, and

Ys 8804 for PAL. CMS sources PAL and Reed rice and the restorers reported in Table 2 seem to be promising material in hybrid rice breeding. ■